

Promoting Zapote bridge as a historical tourist attraction

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Abstract

This study was conducted to assess and provide awareness about the history of Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. Moreover, the researchers aim to promote and advocate tourist sites that can help Cavite build an image that can be the main tourist attraction in the province next to Aguinaldo Shrine. The researchers came up with the idea of studying this to promote Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. This descriptive quantitative research design study used the survey method to determine the respondents' level of awareness and perceptions of Zapote Bridge as a historical site. The respondents in this study are the locals from Zapote: Bacoor and Las Piñas. The results show that most of the respondents belong to age group of 18-24 years old, wherein the majority are either self-employed or students. Most of the respondents are strongly aware of Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction, and they believe that the effective way to promote Zapote Bridge is to conduct a clean-up program and restoration activities, followed by putting up posters and signage and distributing brochures for people's awareness. Based on the result, clean-up and restoration activities must be prioritized to effectively and successfully promote Zapote Bridge. To further utilize the results of the data gathered, the researchers proposed an action plan to further promote the said bridge.

Keywords: Historical tourist attractions; Promotion; Strategies; Effectiveness; Awareness.

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Introduction

The history of Zapote Bridge started with the loss of the revolutionary battle and the opening of the second phase of the war as the Spaniards began their campaign to recapture territories. The revolutionaries then planned a counterattack to stop the Spanish offensive in Cavite. The site of the battle was planned for Zapote Bridge in Bacoor. The Battle of Zapote Bridge was fought from February 17, 1897, until June 13, 1899, as part of the Philippine Revolution. Filipino revolutionary forces led by General Emilio Aguinaldo defeated Spanish forces under the command of Governor-General Camilo de Polavieja. Zapote Bridge is a reminder of Filipino revolutionaries' courage and valor during the bloody battle for freedom (Reyno, 2012). Zapote Bridge is where the second-largest battle of the Philippine-American War occurred. In addition, the bridge is a historic site to honor the battle of the Filipino revolutionaries. Zapote Bridge is a historical landmark and a historical tourist attraction. It is also essential to give credit and attention to the historical background of the Zapote Bridge on the border of Bacoor and Las Piñas. It was one of the places where Filipino heroes fought for Filipinos' freedom (Dacumos, 2012).

According to Salazar (2012), historical tourist attractions must be promoted as studying history is important because it allows us to understand not just our past but also our present. Stearns (2020) added that studying history helps us understand people and societies. It helps us understand change and how the society we live in came to be. He also mentioned that history contributes to moral understanding and provides identity, thus, essential for good citizenship.

The importance of conducting this study is to inform the public about the legacy of the revolution and the importance of this historical site in Cavite. This is also to help sustain the growth and development of Historical Tourist Attractions in Zapote, Bacoor and Las Piñas, and optimistically, Zapote Bridge will be one of them.

The researchers decided to conduct this study to promote Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction for various reasons: the first is to sustain the preservation of the Zapote Bridge. The pride and image of the place can benefit the locals who live near the place. This study focuses on how to promote Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. Furthermore, in promoting Zapote Bridge, it can create employment and business opportunities.

Second, promoting the Zapote Bridge can boost the bridge itself and the place where it is located. It can also promote nearby tourist attractions in Bacoor and Las Pinas. Lastly, suppose the Zapote Bridge is well known enough, the government can provide infrastructure development since many people will visit the Zapote Bridge. Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction has the potential to contribute to economic growth and poverty reduction for a bright future.

Most people are not aware of the importance and relevance of Zapote Bridge. The Zapote Bridge's history has a significant impact during the Spanish Period and on the Filipino revolutionaries who fought for the rights and freedom of Filipinos. The researchers aim to promote Zapote Bridge. The study intends to provide awareness about the history of the Zapote Bridge, including those who fought during the war

Significance of the Study

This study aims to contribute new knowledge, impact, and awareness of Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. Therefore, the following groups of people are seen to benefit from this study:

Local community – By familiarizing the effective ways of marketing a local tourist site, this study will open job opportunities for locals living near the area.

Private sector – The private sector is one of the beneficiaries of the Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction because it can open businesses to accommodate tourists, such as food stalls, souvenir shops, hostels for backpackers, and the like. This will help them have a stable status in life.

Tourism industry in Bacoor and Las Piñas – This will help boost the tourism industry in both cities. Since Cavite is rich in history, we need to include Zapote Bridge as part of the historical tours in Cavite because it may not be known to people outside of Cavite and Las Piñas.

Government – As for the recovery, many people will establish businesses in the area, which will also help increase the number of tourists in the area.

Future researchers – This study will benefit future researchers with treatments and processes not just for future researchers but also for future generations.

Tourism students – This study will benefit the tourism students as they will gain new knowledge about historical tourist attractions, particularly Zapote Bridge. As future tourism professionals, they will be of help in promoting the said attraction and may include this as part of a tour itinerary.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study focuses on promoting Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. Only residents who live either in Bacoor or Las Pinas are the target respondents. Furthermore, tourists of the said bridge are also included as respondents. This study will not cover other problems that are not considered promoting Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. The limitations of this study are the promotional strategies of other tourist attractions as well as the matters and occurrences that may arise in the study which are out of the researchers' control.

Statement of the Problem

This research attempts to find affirmation to the promotion of the Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. More specifically, it seeks to find the answers to the following questions:

- 1) What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Length of residency in the area
 - 1.3 Employment Status
- 2) What is the level of awareness of the locals on the Zapote Bridge as a historical attraction?
- 3) What are the possible ways to promote Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction?
- 4) Based on the results, what action plan can be suggested to promote Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction?

Foreign Literature

Scholars have defined tourist destinations as a concept complete with constructed products and services whose consumption is under the brand name of the destination. The destinations are well-defined geographically and understood by tourists as unique entities and exhibit several core provisions (Marrocu & Paci, 2013). It is also supported by the World Trade Organization (WTO) that a destination is a unique place where a visitor spends at least one night and exhibits tourism products such as attractions, support services, and tourism resources, complete with defined management, physical and administrative boundaries, and a popular image.

Tourist destinations have different categories. These determine the attractiveness of the destination. Tourist destinations establish their presence with exciting or unusual contributions to attractiveness (Abubakar & Mavondo, 2014; Fernández et al., 2020). Different destinations with unique stories like Zapote Bridge can serve to sustain an individual's knowledge based on their interest in historical aspects. Destination marketing identifies what tourists want to see, which is the product and the different methods that are used to attract tourists, which is the promotion (Pike & Page, 2014). Generally, potential tourists like to know in advance about the products, services, and facilities at the destination. Using several forms of promotional activities can lead the department to carry out different ways to attract potential tourists and encourage them to visit the destination.

To be known, a particular destination needs to be promoted because promoting a destination helps to draw the attention of potential tourists and influence people to visit a destination. Therefore, Macloed and Todnem By (2007) outlined the conceptual features combined with sustainable tourism and considered the perception of the public policy context for sustainable tourism. Public policy on tourism means being responsible for planning, development, and promotion to attract tourists to visit their destination (Martínez et al., 2014).

There are three types of promotion which help to modify consumer behavior in the stages of the buying process (Lumen Learning, n.d.). First is informative promotion, which is the most effective at the earlier buying process stages, like attention and comprehension (Kumar & Gupta, 2016). Second is persuasive promotion, which works well by using different media platforms that attract an audience, especially tourists (Moscardo, 2020). The promotion of tourism helps attract the attention of potential tourists, modify the behavior of the existing tourists, and influence them to visit a destination. Third is social media, because it is a two-way communication channel, since companies can enhance promotional efforts through social media (Cortado & Chalmeta, 2016).

All promotion is aimed at creating, with the accumulation of facilities, to ensure the necessary services for the efficient operation and the best possible operation of the industry. For this purpose, promotion is a must. Proper modes of promotion ensure proper growth, competence, and effectiveness. As tourism is growing fast, it has developed from several sectors: formal, informal, public, private and national and international. Initiatives in the tourism industry are aimed at creating awareness and cooperation among people, earning foreign currency, providing employment opportunities, and thereby benefiting people, society, region and country (Pan et al., 2018).

Local Literature

Promotion of tourism in the Philippines can benefit tourists and residents alike by having a guide to the greatest places to visit in Manila. Because Manila is the Philippines' capital and primary gateway, providing a program that highlights various tourist destinations in the area will attract more visitors. The Philippines offers a varied range of tourist attractions derived from natural and cultural history, but not all of them are well-known. The Philippines' history of political instability is the most significant issue affecting tourism. The continuous uncertainty in our country, as well as the possibility of unrest, raises concerns among potential tourists. As a result, in comparison to other countries, the Philippines' performance as an international tourist destination remains mediocre (Nicolas, 2017).

The Philippines was promoted in 2001 with the "WOW Philippines" ad plan, which attracted both domestic and international tourists. As a result, foreign visitors traveled to the Philippines to witness the magnificent sights, people, and culture (Boquet, 2017). Various campaigns and information materials were distributed to raise awareness of places to visit and provide keepsakes for interested guests (Alexandria-Gonzalez, 2016; Negruşa et al., 2015). Tagaytay, Cebu Province, Boracay Islands, and Metro Manila are the most popular locations.

Manila is the capital of the Philippines, and as such, it serves as the primary gateway. It is open to the public. It also provides a diverse choice of tourist destinations for visitors to explore. The Department of Tourism previously organized various trainings and workshops in conjunction with the government's "It's More Fun in the Philippines" initiative to improve the level of service provided to tourists in the Philippines (Boquet, 2017). In addition, they engage in a variety of activities, such as going on field trips and attending international travel exhibitions to attract tourists (Aceron et al., 2018; Gonzales, 2019; Valdez et al., 2017).

The collection of foreign and local studies above provides information on promotional strategies and their proposed study has similarities with the researcher's study in promoting Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. It has brought new opportunities that help tourism promotion strategies improve. The article stated that promotion is done in different ways, such as promotion through proper modes of promotion such as promotions through advanced platforms and using various forms of promotional campaigns and activities. Feature strategy development would create more proper growth, competence, and effectiveness possibility for the success of tourism promotion.

Methodology

The researchers used a descriptive quantitative research design. The survey method determined the level of awareness and determined the respondents' level of perceptions toward Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. The questionnaire was included to gain knowledge of the respondent's views and beliefs. The researchers developed a survey questionnaire based on the research question. Follow up questions in line with the study was asked to deeply understand the respondent's suggestions on how to promote Zapote Bridge.

The respondents in this study are the locals from Zapote: Bacoor and Las Piñas. In this way, the researchers gathered relevant information regarding the study. The respondents are expected to give recommendations and suggestions to better promote the Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. Convenience sampling was used to gather all the data. A total of 100 respondents participated in this study.

The researchers visited the area for an actual observation. After the visit, the questionnaires were distributed to the respondents of locals from Zapote Bridge. The researchers took down notes and carefully analyzed the gathered information. This study utilized percentage and frequency distribution to analyze the responses of 100 respondents. The distribution shows the terms of frequency and percentage of categorical data. The researchers categorized the data into characteristics: demographic profile, level of awareness of the respondents about Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction and suggestions on how to further promote this location.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1. Profile of the respondents based on age

Figure 1 reveals the profile of the respondents based on age. The figure above shows that 8% of the respondents belong to ages 45-54 years old, while 13% of the respondents are from 35-44 years old, 15% are aged 25-34 years old, 19% are ages 55 and up, and the highest percentage of the demographic profile of the respondents is from those aged 18-24 years old, which is 45%.

Figure 2. Profile of the respondents based on residency

Figure 2 reveals the profile of the respondents based on residency. The graph shows that 53% have resided in either Zapote, Bacoor or Las Piñas for 20 years or more. In comparison, 24% are residents living for 5-10 years and lastly with a total of 23% are residents for 1-5 years.

Figure 3. Profile of the respondents based on employment status

Figure 3 shows the employment status of the respondents. The graph shows that 9% of the respondents are currently looking for work, while 12% of the respondents are already retired, while 18% of the respondents are all professional, while 25% of the respondents are self-employed and lastly, the majority with 36% of the respondents are students.

Figure 4. Respondents' level of awareness about Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist destination

Figure 4 shows the level of awareness of the locals on the Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. It shows that 67 out of 100 answered that they are strongly aware of the Zapote Bridge being a historical tourist attraction. On the other hand, 33 out of 100 are strongly not aware of it.

Figure 5. Activities suggested by respondents to promote Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction

Figure 5 reveals the Activities to promote Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. This figure above shows that 85 out of 100 respondents agree that the effective way to promote Zapote Bridge is conducting clean-up and restoration activity, followed by posters, signage, and brochures with 80-82 out of 100 respondents find that those activities are all helpful. While 78 respondents answered blogging, 76 for lights and sounds, 74 both for vlogging and live activities are the activities needed to promote Zapote Bridge. Clean-up and restoration program is perceived to be highly effective in developing tourism promotion; conserving the environment means preserving history and has the potential to lessen the risks of acquiring diseases while effective in providing opportunities. The program is highly effective in promoting historical attractions with sanitation and cleanliness and in ensuring the safety of every local and future tourists (Aquino et al., 2021; Kachniewska, 2015; Manalo, 2016).

Conclusion

More than half of the respondents have resided in Bacoor or Las Pinas for 20 years or more. Majority of the respondents belong to age group 18-24 years old. Most of the respondents are students while some are self-employed. Most of the people in the communities of Bacoor and Las Piñas are strongly aware of Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. This shows that a lot of people are cognizant about the bridge, its history, and importance. Clean-up and restoration are the top choice of the respondents that can help promote Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist destination. Therefore, these activities should be prioritized to promote effectively and successfully the said attraction.

Recommendations

For the locals of Zapote, Bacoor and Las Pinas, the researchers recommend creating private groups or organizations that will oversee a clean-up and restoration program. This will help boost the local government’s tourism strategy to attract more tourists and thus can help with developing more facilities.

For the private business sector in Bacoor and Las Piñas, the researchers recommend utilizing Zapote Bridge's popularity in embracing opportunities in creating businesses, whether small or not. Making Zapote Bridge as a promotional tool will help increase awareness of the said bridge and, at the same time, will help their respective businesses to grow.

For future researchers, they suggest continuing preserving and promoting Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. The researchers further recommend conducting a more detailed study regarding strategies that could help promote Zapote Bridge. To the local government units of Bacoor and Las Piñas, the researchers suggest the local government units of Bacoor and Las Pinas support the residents, private business sectors and future researchers, in all their endeavors to initiate change and to achieve maximum results in promoting Zapote Bridge as a historical tourist attraction. The researchers believed that this bridge has the potential to be one of the reasons for the growth of both the economies and tourism of the area.

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